

NFDI4Objects
Research Data Infrastructure
for the Material Remains of
Human History

Temporary Working Group (TWG)

Proof of Ownership in the Event of Loss: Use-Case for the Minimal Data Set

Chairs: Bernhard Weisser (SMB, MK), Benjamin Streubel (LEIZA)

Members (as of 14.08.2024): Gerrit Brüning (KSW, Text+), Bernhard Fritsch (DAI, KulturGutRetter), Charalampos Georgiadis (ENIGMA), Anja Gerber (TA6, KSW), Peggy Große (Deutsches Museum, NFDI4Memory), Frank von Hagel (SMB, Inst. f. Museumsforschung / Dt. Museumbund), Mario Kliewer (Deutsches Museum, NFDI4Memory), Christoph Klose (SMB, MK), Jens Peters (LVR, Kulturdezernat), Helen Reich (SMB, Referat Digitale Museumsdienste), Max Resch (SMB, MK), Johannes Schäffer (HU Berlin, SODa), Michael Schmauder (LVR Bonn Museum), Alicia Schulz (Archäologisches Museum Hamburg), Katja Sternitzke (SBB, NFDI4Culture)

SC-Decision: 19.07.2024

Designation of Members by the Speaker: 14.08.2024

Bodies Involved: Task Area 2, Task Area 6, LEIZA, Institutions of SMB (MK, IfM, Referat Digitale Museumsdienste), Community Cluster: Collection Management, Temporary Working Group: N4O Object Ontology (OO) & N4O Minimal-Meta-Data-Standards (MMDS)

External Linking: NFDI4Culture, NFDI4Memory, Text+, LVR (Landschaftsverband Rheinland), Archäologisches Museum Hamburg, Deutsches Museum München, ENIGMA, ICOM, Fachgruppe Dokumentation Deutscher Museumbund e.V., Die AG Minimaldatensatz, HU Berlin SODa (Sammlungen, Objekte, Datenkompetenzen), Staatsbibliothek zu Berlin (SBB)

Aims and Objectives

Cultural heritage items are exposed to theft and other forms of loss, even if they are stored in secure rooms. Dangers threaten from outside (burglary, robbery) and inside (abuse of positions of trust). For this reason, the collection management of institutions that store collections requires comprehensive, holistic risk management. The associated digital minimal indexing of the stored objects with regard to unambiguous identification is necessary for two reasons: firstly, the knowledge of the existence of such documentation can act as a deterrent, and secondly, it provides the prerequisite for rapid proof of ownership in the event of loss.

Minimal indexing must include all data that makes an object unambiguously identifiable and traceable. It must be created using digital methods in order to enable rapid access to larger and heterogeneous material holdings. Identifying object data is always important research data at the same time. The aim of the TWG is to evaluate existing recommendations and standards for object data capture with regard to this security-relevant basic information. In addition to guidelines and recommendations (such as the ICOM Object-ID¹, the Security Guidelines for Cultural Property of the Conference of National Cultural

¹ https://icom.museum/wp-content/uploads/2020/12/ObjectID_german.pdf [1.7.2024].

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Institutions², the Spectrum Procedures of the Collection Trust³), the recommendations of the Minimal Data Set Working Group in particular are to be examined for their applicability to unambiguous proof of ownership⁴. The use-case is to be integrated into the process of developing the N4O minimal metadata standards and the N4O object ontology. The inclusion of various cultural collection institutions allows the need for its application to be evaluated across disciplines and genres.

Out of Scope

The requirements and needs of cultural science collections should primarily serve as a starting point. The TWG does not deal with aspects of inventory, content documentation and in-depth cataloguing, even if there may be overlaps with existing documentation projects. It also does not deal with other security-related measures of holistic risk management (e.g. conservation and storage of objects). The issues of data backup, sustainable long-term archiving and user administration are also not dealt with here. No new software solutions are created in connection with the documentation of collections.

² <https://www.silk-tool.de/de/> [1.7.2024].

³ <https://collectiontrust.org.uk/spectrum/procedures/> [1.7.2024].

⁴ <https://wiki.deutsche-digitale-bibliothek.de/pages/viewpage.action?pageId=120422678;www.minimaldatensatz.de> [1.7.2024].

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Intended Work Results

In the event of loss quick proof of ownership of objects is essential. The topic is intended to illustrate the usefulness of digital core data and serve as an application example for the minimum data set, digital reproduction and the use of standardised data. Based on the experiences of the participating collections and the critical evaluation of existing guidelines, the intersections with the basic documentation of objects will be discussed by examining the specifications for mandatory and recommended object information in the aforementioned guidelines. Application examples will be developed with regard to the needs of different object categories and material genres. Both should form the basis for recommendations to be derived from this. The results should ensure that the N4O minimal metadata standards and the N4O object ontology are integrated for this area of security documentation, that they include the necessary object data and that they are applicable in the community.

The TWG aims to build a network that acquires expertise in various issues of security documentation in the context of research data management.

Envisaged Commons Contributions

Whitepaper 1: Comparative analysis of existing recommendations on minimum indexing standards in the area of unambiguous proof of ownership in the event of loss using the example of cultural studies collections.

Whitepaper 2: Use-cases with regard to Whitepaper 1.

Whitepaper 3: Stimulating recommendations for various object groups and procedures with regard to minimum data set.